

ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR AND PERFORMANCE OF ZENITH BANKS IN ENUGU, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This research work, examined organizational citizenship behaviour and performance of money deposit banks in Nigeria. The objectives of the study included to: ascertain how selfless service affects service commitment of employees of Zenith Bank Branches in Enugu State, determine the extent to which courtesy affects quality of service of employees of the selected Zenith Bank Branches in Enugu State, assess the effects of civic virtues on punctuality of the selected Zenith Banks in Enugu, Nigeria, and identify how probity affects customers complaints of selected Zenith Banks in Enugu, Nigeria. The research method adopted by the study was the survey method. The sources of data used were the primary and secondary sources of data. The population of the study was 200 while the sample size of 139 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula. The major instrument of data collection was questionnaire. The data collected were presented in tables using frequencies and percentages and analyzed using the five point Likert scale. The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square distribution formula. The findings included that selfless service has significant positive effect on the behaviour of employees of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc, courtesy, to a large extent has a significant positive effect on the quality of service of employees of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc, civic virtues have significant positive effect on punctuality of the workers of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc and probity has significant positive effect on complaint of the customers of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc. The study concluded that organizational citizenship behaviour has a significant positive effect on the performance of money deposit banks in Nigeria and it was recommended that management of money deposit banks should encourage their workers to adopt

selfless service in their day-to-day activities by giving them orientation on the need for such service, management of money deposit banks should equally encourage their workers to adopt courtesy by letting them know its importance in attracting customers for the organization, civic virtues should be encouraged by the management of money deposit banks through adequate orientation and the management of money deposit banks should encouraged probity among their workers.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behaviour, Organizational Performance

INTRODUCTION

The history of organizational citizenship behavior could be traced back to 1938 when *organizations were first seen as cooperative systems. Belief in the ideals of the organization was indispensable to cooperation and to the spontaneous contributions employees made to other employees and to the organization itself. Bernard (2014) opines that material and monetary compensation were not sufficient to motivate workers to contribute enough for the sustained success of an organization. Barnard (2014) wrote that willingness to cooperate is the antecedent of spontaneous contributions and cooperation whether positive or negative, is the expression of the net satisfactions or dissatisfactions experienced or anticipated through alternative opportunities. What constitutes a good employee in a 21st century workplace? It is important to have good relationships among co-workers. Being helpful and supportive of colleagues in a way that benefits the organization and working towards the organization's goals is likely to improve the performance of employees. Organizational citizenship behavior is referred to a set of discretionary workplace behaviors that exceed one's basic job requirements. They are often described as behaviors that go beyond the call of duty. Research on organizational citizenship behaviour has been extensive since its introduction nearly twenty years back (Bateman & Organ, 2011). The vast majority of organizational citizenship behavior research has focused on the effects of organizational citizenship behaviour on individuals and organizational performance.*

There is a consensus in this particular field that organizational citizenship behavior addresses silent behaviours for organizational enterprises (Barbuto, 2013). Successful organizations have employees who go beyond their formal job responsibilities and freely give off their time and energy to succeed at the assigned job. Such initiative is neither prescribed nor required; yet it contributes to the smooth functioning of the organization. Organizations cannot effectively prosper without their members behaving as good citizens by engaging in all sorts of positive behaviours'. Because of the importance of good citizenship for organizations, understanding the nature and sources of organizational citizenship behavior has long been a high priority for organizational scholars (Organ, 2014) and

remains so. Organ (2014) further elaborated that organizational citizenship behavior can maximize the efficiency and productivity of both the employee and the organization that ultimately contribute to the effective functioning of an organization.

Organizational citizenship behavior has been shown to have a positive impact on employee performance and wellbeing, and this in turn has noticeable flow-on effects on the organization. There is evidence for the widely-held belief that satisfied workers perform better, but this is correlation, not causal. However, certain types of performance — primarily those related to citizenship behavior — will be affected by job satisfaction. Think of workers who are cooperative with their superiors and colleagues, willing to make compromises and sacrifices and are 'easier to work with', workers who 'help out with the extra little things' without complaining (or even offering to do so without being asked) — these behaviors are all encompassed within organizational citizenship behavior. The effects on employee performance are threefold. Firstly, workers who engage in organizational citizenship behavior tend to receive better performance ratings by their managers (Podsakoff, 2009). This could be because employees who engage in organizational citizenship behavior are simply liked more and perceived more favorably (this has become known as the 'halo effect'), or it may be due to more work-related reasons such as the manager's belief that organizational citizenship behavior plays a significant role in the organization's overall success. Regardless of the reason, the second effect is that a better performance rating is linked to gaining rewards (Morrison, 2012) – such as pay increments, bonuses, promotions or work-related benefits. Thirdly, because these employees have better performance ratings and receive greater rewards, when the company is downsizing e.g. during an economic recession, these employees will have a lower chance of being made redundant. Organizational citizenship behavior is linked to lower rates of employee turnover and absenteeism, but on the organizational level increased productivity, efficiency and customer satisfaction, as well as reduced costs, have also been observed (Rush, 2014).

Mackenzie (2012) has stated that organizational citizenship behavior enhances productivity (helping new co-workers; helping colleagues meet deadlines); free up resources, attract and retain good employees through creating and maintaining a friendly, supportive working environment and a sense of belonging. Organizational citizenship behavior creates social capital, enhances better communication and stronger networks, facilitates accurate information transfer and improves efficiency. It is based on this background that this study examined the effect of organizational citizenship behavior on the performance of employees of Zenith Bank Branches in Enugu

Statement of the Problem

Ideally, every organization would like to have employees who abide by the principles of organizational citizenship behavior. This is because when employees assist one another in the work place, the redundant or inactive employees are usually stimulated to perform better. This is because no man is an island and the interactions of the employees usually bring harmony in the organization leading to improved employee performance.

Unfortunately, this situation has not been ideal in the banking industry. Some workers do not offer help to their colleagues when they have high targets that may not be easy to accomplish. This has led to many employees finding it difficult to work in the banking industry for a long period.

The effect or consequences of not adopting Organizational Citizenship Behavior is that it could lead to lack of employees' commitment as a result of lack of altruism in the organization. Another effect of not adopting organizational citizenship behavior is that it could lead to a decline in the quality of service of the employees as a result of lack of courtesy. Furthermore increase in customers' complaints is another effect of not adopting organizational citizenship behavior in an organization as a result of lack of probity.

Objectives of the Study

1. Determine the extent to which courtesy affects quality of service of selected Zenith Bank in Enugu, Nigeria

Assess how civic virtues affects punctuality of selected Zenith Bank in Enugu, Nigeria

2. Identify how probity affect customers complaints of selected Zenith Bank in Enugu, Nigeria

Research Questions

- 1. To what extent has courtesy affected the quality of service of selected Zenith Bank in Enugu, Nigeria?*
- 2. What is the effect of Civic virtues on punctuality of selected Zenith Bank in Enugu, Nigeria?*
- 3. What is the effect of probity on complaints of the customers of the selected Zenith Bank in Enugu, Nigeria?*

Statement of Hypotheses

- 1. There is no significant relationship between courtesy and quality of employees of selected Zenith Bank Branches in Enugu State.*

2. *There is no significant relationship between civic virtues and punctuality of selected Zenith Bank Branches in Enugu State.*
3. *There is no significant relationship between probity and customers complaints of selected Zenith Bank Branches in Enugu State.*

Concept of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is the technical psychological term for what can simply be defined as the compilation of individual behaviors in a group setting. Organizational citizenship behavior was first defined by Dennis Organ in 1988 as “an individual behavior which is not rewarded by a formal reward system but that, when combined with the same behavior in a group, results in effectiveness.” In the business world, organizational citizenship behavior has been linked to work productivity, employee effectiveness, and other factors which can impact a business in the short or long term.

Common examples of organizational citizenship behavior occur when employees are grouped together, while others may occur on a regular basis or as part of a special or temporary assignment. For example, employees in the marketing department will display organizational citizenship behavior because they are co-workers in the same department; employees who are put together for a temporary work assignment will also display organizational citizenship behavior, albeit on a temporary basis.

Types of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

OCB can be classified into five common behaviours and it is suggested that, when these common behaviours are exhibited in a group setting, it will lead to effectiveness. In the context of business, this means that the five most common organizational citizenship behaviours will lead to more productivity and more effective work. Although today psychologists recognize dozens of other. Common positive organizational citizenship behaviours†; the five defined by Organ in 1988 are still considered to be the most significant. The five most common behaviours† are: selfless service, courtesy, probity, conscientiousness, and civic virtue.

1. Selfless Service

Selfless service is defined as the desire to help or otherwise assist another individual, while not expecting a reward in compensation for that assistance (Mullins, 2016). A common example outside of a business setting would be someone who drives a neighbour to work when their car has broken down, while not expecting gas money or favors in compensation. In a business setting, selfless service is generally related to the work or project that the business group is working on. Someone exhibiting selfless service in a group setting might volunteer to work on certain work-related projects, voluntarily helping or assisting other employees with their work

or with other tasks, and volunteering to do additional work in order to help other employees reduce their own workload.

Selfless service in the workplace leads to productivity and effectiveness because it encourages good inter-employee relations; it can also reduce the stress load on other employees, such as those who are overwhelmed without a little bit of help, which will in turn increase productivity.

Conceptually, selfless service involves voluntarily helping others with, or preventing the occurrence of, work-related problems. The first part of this definition (helping others with work-related problems) includes Organ's selfless service, peace-making, and cheerleading dimensions (Organ, 2009), interpersonal helping (Graham, 2011), the helping others constructs from George and Brief (2008) and George and Jones (2010).

The second part of the definition captures Organ (2009) notion of courtesy, which involves helping others by taking steps to prevent the creation of problems for coworkers.

2. Courtesy

Courtesy is defined as behaviour which is polite and considerate towards other people (Steiner, 2013). Courtesy outside of a workplace setting includes behaviour such as asking how someone's morning has been or asking after the welfare of a neighbour's child.

In a business context, courtesy is usually exhibited through behaviours such as inquiring about personal subjects that a coworker has previously brought up, asking if a coworker is having any trouble with a certain work-related project, and informing coworkers about prior commitments or any other problems that might cause them to reduce their workload or be absent from work.

Courtesy not only encourages positive social interactions between employees, which improve the work environment, but also they can reduce any potential stress that might occur from employees who do not have the courtesy to inform their coworkers about issues such as upcoming absences from work—and so on.

3. Probity

Probity is defined as exhibiting no negative behaviour when something does not go as planned or when something is being perceived as annoying, difficult, frustrating or otherwise negative (Podsakoff, 2010). Outside of a business context, probity is most commonly associated with sports and games—poor probity, for example, might occur when a player on a soccer team swears, stomps and argues when their team loses a soccer game. In the context of business, probity is usually related to potential complaints about work or workloads in addition to negativity surrounding work-related surprises. For example: Imagine employees who submit

their proposal to their superior may be expecting it to be well-received and accepted—it is rejected, instead, and the employees display probity by not complaining about the situation to other coworkers.

Probity is a form of citizenship behavior that has received much less attention in the literature. Organ (1990), has defined probity as “a willingness to tolerate the inevitable inconveniences and impositions of work without complaining.” However, his definition seems somewhat narrower than the label of this construct would imply. For example, in our opinion good probity are people who not only do not complain when they are inconvenienced by others, but also maintain a positive attitude when things do not go their way. They are not offended when others do not follow their suggestions, are willing to sacrifice their personal interest for the good of the work group, and do not take the rejection of their ideas personally.

4. *Conscientiousness*

Conscientiousness is defined as behaviour that suggests a reasonable level of self-control and discipline, which extends beyond the minimum requirements expected in that situation (Marcus, 2012). In the context of a business setting, conscientiousness is observed when an employee not only meets his or her employer’s requirements—such as coming to work on time and completing assignments on time—but exceeds them. Exceeding these requirements, and thereby showing conscientiousness, could be observed—for example—by an employee planning ahead to ensure that they, and their coworkers, do not become overwhelmed in their work.

5. *Civic Virtue*

Civic virtue is defined as behaviour which exhibits how well a person represents an organization with which he is associated, and how well that person supports his organization outside of an official capacity (Schuller, 2015). For example, how well someone represents his business and how he may support that business are all examples of someone's civic virtue. Examples of civic virtue in a business setting include speaking positively about the business to friends, family and acquaintances. Civic virtue encourages a sense of community within a business setting, which has been shown to be linked to job performance and job satisfaction in employees. Employees who feel a stronger connection with their place of employment are more likely to be productive and effective workers, when compared to those who do not share a sense of community.

Consequences of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

Although the majority of the early research efforts focused on the antecedents of citizenship behaviour, more recent research has devoted an increasing amount of attention to the consequences of OCBs. More specifically, recent research has focused on two key issues: (a) the effects of OCBs on managerial evaluations of performance and judgments regarding pay raises, promotions, etc., and (b) the effects of OCBs on organizational performance and success. In the next section, we will examine the literature on the effects that OCBs have on these two areas.

A key tenet of Organ's original definition of organizational citizenship behavior (Organ, 2016) is that, when aggregated over time and people, such behaviour enhances organizational effectiveness. For many years, this assumption went untested and its acceptance was based mostly on its conceptual plausibility than direct empirical evidence (Podsakoff, 2010). Conceptually, there are several reasons why citizenship behaviors' might influence organizational effectiveness (George, 2008). However, despite the intuitive plausibility of the assumption that OCBs contribute to the effectiveness of work teams and organizations, this issue has received little empirical attention.

This is surprising because much of the interest in organizational citizenship and its related constructs stems from the belief that these behaviours enhance organizational performance. Indeed, although over 160 studies have been reported in the literature to identify the antecedents of OCBs, to our knowledge, only five studies have attempted to test whether these behaviors' influence organizational effectiveness. Perhaps the first study to explore whether citizenship behaviour is related to group or organizational effectiveness was Karambayya (2017).

Tips to Encourage OCB in the Workplace

The following are some other tips to encourage OCB in the workplace:

1. Office social environment

A working environment that promotes or is conducive to employees demonstrating OCB. Certain types of group norms (e.g., everyone should only do the minimum amount of work required; everyone should mind his/her own business and no one should talk to the supervisor) can stifle worker initiative and spontaneity, and this will decrease incidents of OCB. Group norms may be difficult to break but other things can be done to make workers more social — such as encouraging staff to attend office functions or having more office functions, or office-wide birthday lunches.

2. Supervisor awareness

Training or educating management about OCB will make them more aware of employee displays of OCB. They may choose to include OCB in their performance appraisals, or devise their own casual/informal reward system to encourage OCB.

3. Hiring practices

Though the impact of personality on OCB is small, an outgoing, attentive, enthusiastic employee with a positive outlook and 'can do' attitude will be more inclined to engage in OCB. If psychometric testing is a part of your interview/hiring process, consider looking out for traits related to OCB, and have these staff motivate others.

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Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Demerits

There are three main issues to be cautious of when promoting OCB in your workplace.

1. Discrimination

Be especially wary of implicit gendered expectations—research has shown that men are rewarded for OCB more than women (Heilman & Chen, 2015), as women are expected to engage in certain types of citizenship behaviors (such as being altruistic and courteous) more than men.

2. Organizational justice

In addition to the gender bias, if some supervisors reward OCB more than others, perceived unfairness may increase among certain clusters of employees. This will not only lead to a decrease in OCB among those not rewarded for it, but may have other side effects related to perceived injustice, such as an increase in counterproductive behavior (e.g. theft, absenteeism) (Marcus & Schuler, 2004).

3. Habituation

If OCB is rewarded regularly, you may find that OCB levels will rise across the organization over time. What was once considered OCB may become an internalized organizational norm, and is no longer spontaneous and voluntary but expected

of workers. Research into this phenomenon, termed citizenship pressure, is relatively recent, and though contested, it may impact negatively on employee stress levels (Bolino, Turnley, Gilstrap & Suazo, 2010).

The Concept of Employee Performance

Employee performance refers to whether a person executes his job, duties and responsibilities well. Many companies assess their employees' performance on an annual or quarterly basis in order to define certain areas that need improvement. Performance is a critical factor in organizational success (Conway, 2009).

Clegg (2012) posits that employee performance is the job-related activities expected of a worker and how well those activities were executed. Many business personnel directors assess the employee performance of each staff member on an annual or quarterly basis in order to help them identify suggested areas for improvement.

A Learning Management System can be a major influence in boosting employee performance by helping lower the training costs and increase the training effectiveness. You will be able to assign specific training to the employees who need it most, track when it has been completed, and have automated reporting to show you how well the course information was retained.

Metrics for Measuring Employee Performance

Three basic metrics often used by small business owners are:

- i. Productivity Metrics.** Productivity is the bottom line for any employee, regardless of the job. It's the amount of work an employee accomplishes in a specific amount of time, such as a workday or week. Productivity should rise as an employee gains experience and proficiency. Productivity is often measured using numbers, such as selling or producing a certain number of widgets, or making a certain number of sales calls.
- ii. Efficiency Metrics.** This is a companion to productivity, measuring how much effort and/or expense is required for an employee to maximize productivity. Coming up with a creative solution to cut costs, or reduce the number of mistakes made in production, or increasing the accuracy of data entry, are just a few examples.
- iii. Training Metrics.** Good training programs can boost productivity and efficiency when they are aimed at boosting specific performance outcomes. Written tests or post-training surveys are two ways to immediately evaluate the impact of your training initiatives. Longer-term training success will show up as improved results in your productivity and efficiency metrics.

Theoretical Framework

Five factor model of Organizational Citizenship Behavior

These models were proposed by Organ (1988), he proposed that factors are necessary for OCB. They include;

1. Leadership and organizational citizenship Behaviours (OCB)

Transactional and transformational leadership are seen in two main dimensions of leadership style in many researches. The transformational leadership style is complementary to the transactional style and likely to be ineffective in the total absence of a transactional relationship between leaders and subordinates (Bass and Avolio, 1990; Goodwin, 2001). The difference is that transactional leaders use rewards as a control mechanism to carry out the exchange relationship that is explicitly established to externally motivate followers, whereas transformational leaders use rewards as a component of a system designed to increase followers' commitment and internally motivate followers (Goodwin et al., 2001; Rafferty and Griffin, 2004).

2. Personality traits and organizational citizenship Behaviors (OCB)

Personality traits refer to enduring patterns of thought, emotion and behavior that are not likely to change over time and explain people's behavior across different situations (Costa and McCrae, 1989; Funder, 2001). The five-factor model of personality (FFM) or "big-five" has influenced the field of personality during the last two decades, providing a significant degree of convergence in the trait-factor analytic psychology (Robertson and Callinan, 1998). The five factors are usually labeled extraversion (sociable vs. introverted), agreeableness (cooperative versus competitive), conscientiousness (organized and planful versus unorganized and careless), emotional stability (emotional stability versus instability) and openness to experience (intellectual curiosity versus preference for routine) (Costa and McCrae, 1989).

3. Organizational structure and organizational citizenship Behaviors (OCB)

Organizational structure can be thought of as a set of decisions that are made regarding a variety of organizational areas such as the amount of specialization present in tasks, the amount of autonomy present, or the type of interdependencies present. While it is

possible to examine each decision as a separate dimension of organizational structure, several organizational typologies exist (Mintzberg, 1979; Miles and Snow, 1978) that contrast different organization types based on how they match a profile of different decisions. Burns and Stalker (1961) proposed a contingency model for organizations that position organizations on a continuum anchored at one end by the mechanistic organization and at the other by organic organization.

4. Organizational culture and organizational citizenship Behaviors (OCB)

Hofstede (1980) defined “**culture**” as the collective mental programming or the mind that distinguishes the members of one group from another. He argued that culture is a property of groups and that country boundary is typically coincident with cultural boundaries. National culture influences how members of groups think about what is proper, civilized behavior and influences how one acts toward strangers and colleagues, how one addresses others and how one interacts socially. Hofstede (1980) identified four dimensions of national culture.

Power distance is a measure of the inequality between leaders and followers and the extent to which this inequality is accepted.

Uncertainty avoidance characterizes the extent to which ambiguity and uncertainty are tolerable.

Masculinity vs. femininity (for example, achievement versus relationship orientation) is a measure of the extent to which achievement and success are valued rather than caring for others and quality of life.

Empirical Review

Extent Courtesy has Affected Quality of Service of Employees

The effect of courtesy on quality of service of employees was studied by Adelabu (2017), in Lagos state. The study was carried out using a population of 185 employees using the secondary source of data. The statistical package for the social science (SPSS) was adopted in the analysis and it was found that courtesy affects the quality of service of employees to a large extent.

Ovie (2015), carried out a study in Edo State on the degree of relationship between courtesy and quality of service of employees. In the study a population of 205 employees was studied using the **person product moment correlation (PPMC)** in the analysis and it was found that courtesy has a significant relationship with quality of service of employees.

In a related study carried out in Rivers State by Ebieri (2016) on the relationship between courtesy and quality of service of employees, a population of 270 employees was studied using the survey method of research and the questionnaire as the major

instrument of data collection. The spearman rank order correlation was used in the analysis and it was found that courtesy has a significant relationship with quality of service of employees.

Effect of Civic Virtues on Punctuality of the Workers

In a study carried out at the University of California, Los Angeles by Spencer (2015) on the effect of civic virtues on punctuality of the workers of Financial Institutions, a population of 450 employees was studied using the survey method of research data collection. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used in the analysis and it was found that civic virtues have a positive effect on punctuality of the workers of financial institutions.

Furthermore, Roberts (2014) carried out a study in Lagos State on the effect of civic virtues on the punctuality of workers of an organization. In the study a population of 125 employees was studied using the survey method of research and the questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The T-test was used in the analysis and it was found that civic virtues has a positive effect on punctuality of workers of organization.

In a related study, carried out by Okoye (2013), in Enugu state on the effect of civic virtues on the punctuality of workers of organization. A population of 185 employees was studied using the survey method of research and the questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection and it was found that civic virtues has a positive effect on punctuality of workers of organization.

Effect of Probity on Customers' Complaints

In a study carried out in Lagos state by Williams (2013), on the degree of relationship between probity and reduction in customers complaint, a population of 280 employees was studied using the survey method of research and the questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was used in the analysis and it was found that the probity has a significant relationship with reduction in customers' complaint.

In a related study carried out by Terry (2012), in London on the relationship between probity and reduction in customers' complaint, a population of 390 employees was studied using the survey method of research and the questionnaire as the instrument of data collection. The regression method was used in the analysis and it was found that probity has a significant relationship with customers' complaint.

Finally, Akintola (2013), studied the relationship between probity and reduction in customers' complaint, in the study a population of 190 employees was studied using the survey method of research and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in the analysis and it was found that probity has a significant relationship with customers' complaint.

Methodology

The study adopted survey research design. Questionnaire was the major instruments of data collection.

Test of Hypothesis One

H_0 : Courtesy to a large extent does not have a significant positive effect on quality of service of employees of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc

Constructing the test statistics, we have

Response	O _i	E _i	(o _i – e _i)	(o _i – e _i) ²	(O _i – e _i) ² / e _i
Strongly agree	45	25.6	19.4	376.36	14.70
Agree	60	25.6	34.4	1183.36	46.22
Undecided	11	25.6	-14.6	213.16	8.33
Disagree	4	25.6	-21.6	466.56	18.22
Strongly disagree	8	25.6	-17.6	309.76	12.11
Total	128				

The calculated value = **99.57**. The degree of freedom, $n - 1 = 5 - 1 = 4$ **degrees of freedom**.

The level of significance is **0.05**.

The critical value at 4 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance is **9.49**.

The calculated chi-square value (99.57) is greater than the critical value (9.49).

Test of Hypothesis Two

H_0 : Civic virtues do not have a significant positive effect on punctuality of the workers of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc

Constructing the test statistics, we have

Response	O _i	E _i	(o _i – e _i)	(o _i – e _i) ²	(O _i – e _i) ² / e _i
Strongly agree	80	25.6	54.4	2959.36	115.6
Agree	10	25.6	–15.6	243.36	9.51
Undecided	15	25.6	–10.6	112.36	4.39
Disagree	13	25.6	–12.6	158.76	6.20
Strongly disagree	10	25.6	–15.6	243.36	9.51
Total	128				145.21

The calculated value = 145.21. The degree of freedom, $n-1 = 5-1 = 4$ degree of freedom. The level of significance is = 0.05. The critical value at 4 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance is 9.49. The calculated or chi-square value (145.21) is greater than the critical value (9.49).

Test of Hypothesis Two

Research hypothesis four seeks to ascertain the effect of probity on complaints of the customer of the selected Zenith Bank Branches in Enugu state. The research hypothesis is restated in null form:

H_{02} :

Probity does not have significant positive effect on complaints of the customers of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc.

Constructing the test statistics, we have:

Response	O _i	E _i	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	(O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
Strongly agree	76	25.6	50.40	2540.16	99.22
Agree	20	25.6	-5.60	31.36	1.22
Undecided	12	25.6	-13.6	184.96	7.22
Disagree	15	25.6	-10.6	112.36	4.39
Strongly disagree	5	25.6	-20.6	424.36	16.58
Total	128				128.63

The calculated value = 128.63. The degree of freedom, $n-1 = 5-1 = 4$ degree of freedom. The level of significance is = 0.05. The critical value at 4 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance is 9.49. The calculated or chi-square value (128.63) is greater than the critical value (9.49).

Discussion of Findings

Discussion Based on Hypothesis One

Courtesy to a large extent has a significant positive effect on the commitment of employees of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc. The statement was confirmed to be true in the test of hypothesis two and review of related literature. The evidence is shown in the calculated value (99.57) which is greater than the critical value (9.49). This finding was in line with the empirical review of Ovie (2015), who carried out a research on the extent courtesy affects commitment of employees. It was found that courtesy to a large extent has a significant positive effect on quality of service of employees.

Discussion Based on Hypothesis Two

Civic virtues have significant positive effect on punctuality of workers. The statement was confirmed to be true in the test of hypothesis three and review of related literature. The evidence is shown in the calculated value (145.21) which is greater than the critical value (9.49). This finding was in line with Okoye (2013), who carried out a research on the effect of civic virtues on punctuality of workers of organization. It was found that civic virtues have significant positive effect on punctuality of workers of organization.

Discussion Based on Hypothesis 3

Probity has significant positive effect on complaint of the customers. The statement was confirmed to be true in the test of hypothesis four and review of related literature. The evidence is shown in the calculated value (128.63) which is greater than the critical value (9.49). This findings was in line with Terry (2012), who carried out a research on the effect of probity on complaints of customers. It was found that probity has a significant positive effect on customers' complaint.

Findings

1. Courtesy to a large extent has a significant positive effect on the quality of service of employees of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc.
 - employees of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc. $\chi^2 (4, n = 128) = 99.57, P = 0.05$.
2. Civic virtues have significant positive effect on punctuality of the workers of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc.
 - $\chi^2 (4, n = 128) = 145.21, P = 0.05$.
3. Probity has significant positive effect on complaint of the customers of Zenith Bank Nig. Plc.
 - $\chi^2 (4, n = 128) = 128.63, P = 0.05$.

Conclusion

Organizational citizenship behaviour has many advantages. Several of them can be mentioned like improving organization relationships among employees, improving organization results, increasing job satisfaction, improving work performance, environmental protection etc. It is emphasized that organizational citizenship behavior is not the most important part of the work performance, individual can engage in organizational citizenship behavior but if the work result is not good then organizational citizenship behavior efforts are not so important. Employee training can improve level of organizational citizenship behavior, and

encourage employees to involve in extra activities or to help other employees to act like citizens. In an organization with high quality workers, only way to be distinguished is to perform citizenship behavior. The researcher therefore concludes that organizational citizenship behavior has a significant positive effect on the performance of money deposit banks in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Management of money deposit banks should equally encourage their workers to adopt courtesy by letting them know its importance in attracting customers for the organization.
2. Civic virtues should be encouraged by management of money deposit banks through adequate orientation.
3. The management of money deposit banks should encouraged probity among their workers

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